

Birefringence measurements of substrate materials and coatings for Einstein Telescope

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Abstract

Given the planned tenfold improvement in sensitivity of the future Einstein Telescope, the birefringence of optical elements (substrates and coatings) is becoming an important optical parameter to be measured. A sensitive optical polarimeter has been developed at the Department of Physics and Earth Sciences of the University of Ferrara and INFN - Ferrara Section, Italy to measure ellipticities and rotations induced by substrates and coatings on a linearly polarised laser beam with wavelength $\lambda = 1064$ nm both in transmission and reflection. The sensitivity in optical path difference, both in transmission and in reflection, is $S_{\mathcal{D}} \approx 10^{-12}$ m/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$. The technique takes advantage of both heterodyne detection and of time-dependent signals (ellipticity and rotations) induced by two co-rotating half-wave plates. The method is demonstrated on some crystalline silicon samples and high-reflectivity coatings. Some examples are reported.

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Introduction

With the increasing sensitivity of future third gravitational wave detectors, the birefringence Δn of substrates and its uniformity across the laser beam’s cross section is becoming an issue as was seen in the KAGRA interferometer [1]. One of the critical optical elements is the substrate of the input test masses of the two interferometer arms. These substrates are thick, of the order of several tens of centimeters, and the beam spot size is rather large, covering a significant portion of the substrate. Mirror coatings also present a birefringence map. The characterisation of both the substrates and the reflective coatings, in order to learn how to grow them with minimum birefringence, is mandatory.

Birefringence vs. dichroism

It is generally assumed that the index of refraction n of a substrate medium is uniform and that, at least in a plane perpendicular to the beam propagation, the index of refraction does not depend on

the polarisation direction: given two perpendicular directions, \parallel and \perp , the difference of the index of refraction $n_{\parallel} - n_{\perp} = \Delta n$ for light polarised along the \parallel and \perp directions is zero.

The effect of a birefringence on a linearly polarised beam of light propagating through a medium of path length L is a phase difference $\Delta\phi$ of the electric field components along the \parallel and \perp directions. This phase difference results in the electric field describing an ellipse whose ratio of the minor to major axes is the modulus of the ellipticity ψ . Given an input electric field $\vec{\mathbf{E}}_{\gamma}$ oriented along the X axis (see Figure 1, left)

$$\vec{\mathbf{E}}_{\gamma} = E_{\gamma} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

and a birefringent medium whose \parallel axis forms an angle ϑ with the X axis, the phase shift $\Delta\phi$ (we will assume $|\Delta\phi| \ll 1$) between the \parallel and \perp components of $\vec{\mathbf{E}}_{\gamma}$ is

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \int_L \Delta n dz. \quad (2)$$

The output electric field can then be approximated to first order as

$$\vec{\mathbf{E}}'_{\gamma} \approx E_{\gamma} \begin{pmatrix} 1 + i\frac{\Delta\phi}{2} \cos 2\vartheta \\ i\frac{\Delta\phi}{2} \sin 2\vartheta \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

The ellipticity ψ , defined as the ratio of the minor to major axis of the ellipse generated by the electric field $\vec{\mathbf{E}}'_{\gamma}$, is then

$$\psi \approx i\frac{\pi}{\lambda} \sin 2\vartheta \int_L \Delta n dz. \quad (4)$$

and can be treated as an imaginary number.

Figure 1: Left: ellipticity $|\psi| = a/b$ induced by a birefringent medium whose axis is at an angle ϑ with respect to the incident electric field. Right: rotation ϵ induced by a linear dichroism whose axis is at an angle ϑ with respect to the incident electric field.

More in general, the index of refraction is a complex number: $\tilde{n} = n + i\kappa$. The imaginary term κ , known as the extinction coefficient, describes the absorption of a medium. If, given two perpendicular directions \parallel and \perp , the difference $\Delta\kappa = \kappa_{\parallel} - \kappa_{\perp} \neq 0$ the medium is said to have a linear dichroism, that is a polarisation-dependent absorption. The electric field amplitude of a plane wave propagating

along the Z axis in a uniform medium is described by $E(z) = E e^{i\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}(n+i\kappa)z}$ resulting in an exponential decay of the electric field characterised by the exponent $Q = -\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}\kappa z$.

In analogy to (2), by defining a differential attenuation of the electric field ΔQ

$$\Delta Q = -\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \int_L \Delta\kappa dz, \quad (5)$$

after a length L the electric field of a linearly polarised beam of light forming an angle ϑ with the || direction of the dichroic medium can be approximated with

$$\vec{E}'_\gamma \approx E_\gamma \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \frac{\Delta Q}{2} \cos 2\vartheta \\ -\frac{\Delta Q}{2} \sin 2\vartheta \end{pmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

The X and Y components of \vec{E}'_γ (the Y component is now a real quantity) are still in phase resulting in a linear polarisation whose direction, though, is rotated by an angle $\varepsilon \approx -(\Delta Q/2) \sin 2\vartheta$

$$\varepsilon \approx -\frac{\pi}{\lambda} \sin 2\vartheta \int_L \Delta\kappa dz. \quad (7)$$

and is treated as a real number. This is shown in Figure 1, right.

Note that the measurement of the output power after an analyser oriented along the Y does not allow to discriminate the contributions of a birefringence and a dichroism. In the following we will describe how to distinguish between an ellipticity and a rotation.

Measurement method

Two crossed polarisers set to maximum extinction (with extinction ratio σ^2) with a birefringent medium between them generating an ellipticity ψ given by equation (4) will transmit a power P_{out}

$$P_{\text{out}} = P_0 [\sigma^2 + |\psi|^2]. \quad (8)$$

A typical value for the extinction ratio of a pair of good polarisers is $\sigma^2 \lesssim 10^{-7}$. A static measurement proves to be difficult in that $\sigma^2 \sim |\psi|^2$. Furthermore any optical element between the two crossed polarisers will contribute to ψ making it very difficult to separate the effect of the substrate from the other optical elements. From equation (2) it is clear that small ellipticities add up algebraically. Therefore by adding a time dependent known ellipticity $\eta(t)$ to ψ and modulating in time the substrate ellipticity $\psi = \psi(t)$ itself, P_{out} now results in

$$P_{\text{out}}(t) = P_0 [\sigma^2 + |\psi(t) + \eta(t)|^2] = P_0 \{ \sigma^2 + |\eta(t)|^2 + \mathcal{R}e[2\eta(t)\psi^*(t)] + |\psi(t)|^2 \} \quad (9)$$

linearising the output power as a function of the desired ellipticity. Furthermore, the time dependence (typically sinusoidal) of both $\eta(t)$ and $\psi(t)$ generates a well-defined Fourier spectrum with the components deriving from the double product $\eta(t)\psi(t)$ far from the DC component where noise is generally higher. Indeed, if $\eta(t) = i\eta_0 \cos \omega_m t$ and $\psi(t) = i\psi_0 \cos \omega_\psi t$ the dominant Fourier components of $P_{\text{out}}(t)$ will be (here we neglect terms of order $|\psi(t)|^2$ and higher)

$$\tilde{P}_{\text{out}}(DC) = P_0 \left(\sigma^2 + \frac{\eta_0^2}{2} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\tilde{P}_{\text{out}}(\omega_m + \omega_\psi) = \tilde{P}_{\text{out}}(\omega_m - \omega_\psi) = P_0 \eta_0 \psi_0 \quad (11)$$

$$\tilde{P}_{\text{out}}(2\omega_m) = P_0 \frac{\eta_0^2}{2} \quad (12)$$

from which one can determine $\psi_0 = \frac{\pi}{\lambda} \int \Delta n dL$ as

$$\psi_0 = \frac{\pi}{\lambda} \int \Delta n dL = \frac{\tilde{P}_{\text{out}}(\omega_m + \omega_\psi) + \tilde{P}_{\text{out}}(\omega_m - \omega_\psi)}{\tilde{P}_{\text{out}}(2\omega_m)} \frac{\eta_0}{4}. \quad (13)$$

The ellipticity modulation $\eta(t)$ is obtained with a photo-elastic resonant modulator working at $\nu_m = 50$ kHz and the modulation of $\psi(t)$ is obtained by rotating the polarisation direction using two half-wave plates [2]. In practice, two lock-in amplifiers demodulating $P_{\text{out}}(t)$ at ω_m and $2\omega_m$ are used to extract the components at $\omega_m \pm \omega_\psi$ and at $2\omega_m$.

It is interesting to note that the presence of a rotation $\varepsilon(t)$ does not affect the ellipticity measurement when using an ellipticity modulator. In fact, ellipticity is an imaginary quantity whereas a rotation is real. Therefore the power output in the presence of both a rotation and an ellipticity with an ellipticity modulator will be

$$P_{\text{out}}(t) = P_0 \left\{ \sigma^2 + |\varepsilon(t) + \psi(t) + \eta(t)|^2 \right\} = P_0 \left\{ \sigma^2 + \varepsilon^2(t) + |\eta(t)|^2 + \mathcal{R}e[2\eta(t)\psi^*(t)] + |\psi(t)|^2 \right\} : \quad (14)$$

the modulation $\eta(t)$ does not beat with the rotation $\varepsilon(t)$. Introducing a rotation modulation $\varphi(t)$ at a frequency ω_F with a Faraday rotator, for example, one can simultaneously and independently measure rotations and ellipticities:

$$P_{\text{out}}(t) = P_0 \left\{ \sigma^2 + |\varepsilon(t) + \varphi(t) + \psi(t) + \eta(t)|^2 \right\} = \quad (15)$$

$$= P_0 \left\{ \sigma^2 + \varphi^2(t) + |\eta(t)|^2 + \varepsilon^2(t) + |\psi(t)|^2 + 2\varphi(t)\varepsilon(t) + \mathcal{R}e[2\eta(t)\psi^*(t)] \right\}. \quad (16)$$

Transmission measurements

In Figure 2 a scheme of the polarimeter for measuring the birefringence of a substrate in transmission is shown.

Figure 2: Scheme of the polarimeter for transmission measurements. The linearly polarised 1064 nm beam passes through the rotating half-wave plate L_1 making the polarisation rotate at a frequency $2\nu_w$. The induced ellipticity due to the substrate will be time dependent resulting in a Fourier component at a frequency $4\nu_w$. The second half-wave plate L_2 stops the rotating polarisation allowing measurements in extinction. The ellipticity modulator adds a known ellipticity $\eta(t)$ to $\psi(t)$ linearising $\psi(t)$. By demodulating the signal from PDE at the modulator frequency one can extract $\psi(t)$. The 532 nm beam is used for alignment purposes and the magnetic field for calibration.

Both 1064-nm and 532-nm wavelengths are used. The actual ellipticity measurement of the sample is performed with the 1064 nm laser whereas the 532 nm wavelength is used to align the rotating half-wave plates L_1 and L_2 as will be described shortly. Both wavelengths are polarised by the input polariser. To modulate the ellipticity induced by the sample at 1064 nm, a half-wave plate for 1064 nm

rotating at a frequency $\nu_w = 2$ Hz generates a rotating polarisation at a frequency $2\nu_w$. Given the dependence of the induced ellipticity of equation (4) on the angle ϑ between the \parallel axis and the polarisation direction, the ellipticity signal will be modulated at a frequency $4\nu_w = 8$ Hz. A second rotating half-wave plate L_2 at 1064 nm, phase locked to L_1 , stops the rotating polarisation allowing extinction. The photo-elastic ellipticity modulator adds an ellipticity $\eta(t)$ to the ellipticity induced by the sample $\psi(t)$. Finally, the light passes through the analyser set to extinction. A Faraday rotator for rotation measurements is also present in the polarimeter between the ellipticity modulator and the analyser but is not shown and will not be discussed further in this paper. A rotating 2.5 T, 82 cm long, dipolar magnetic field typically rotating at $\nu_B = 0.5$ Hz is also present between the two rotating half-wave plates to generate a known ellipticity for calibration purposes at a frequency $4\nu_w \pm 2\nu_B$ (the sign depends on the relative rotation direction of the half-wave plates and the magnetic field).

Systematics

As discussed in reference [3], the rotating half-wave plates generate a spurious ellipticity $\psi_{\text{spurious}}(t)$ at various harmonics of the rotating wave plates, due to several causes. A general expression of the total ellipticity signal observed with the scheme in Figure 2, excluding the magnetic field effect, is

$$\psi_{\text{total}}(t) = \psi(t) + \psi_{\text{spurious}}(t) = i\psi_0 \sin 4\vartheta(t) + i\frac{\alpha_1(t)}{2} \sin [2\vartheta(t) + 2\vartheta_1] + i\frac{\alpha_2(t)}{2} \sin [2\vartheta(t) + 2\vartheta_2] \quad (17)$$

where $\vartheta(t) = \omega_w t$ in the frame of Figure 1, $\alpha_{1,2}(t)$ represent the instantaneous phase differences from π given by the two half-wave plates and $\vartheta_{1,2}$ represent the angles of the \parallel axes of the two wave plates with respect to the input polarisation direction at $t = 0$. The α 's are time dependent due to the structural and alignment defects that are summarised below and thoroughly discussed in reference [3]; their time dependence contains harmonics of the rotation frequency ν_w . The most dangerous harmonic in $\psi_{\text{spurious}}(t)$ is clearly the 4-th where the sample signal $\psi(t)$ appears. From equation (17) a 4-th harmonic of ν_w can be generated in $\psi_{\text{spurious}}(t)$ if $\alpha_{1,2}(t)$ has a second harmonic. By expanding $\alpha_{1,2}(t)$ in terms of $\cos \vartheta(t)$ one can write

$$\alpha_{1,2}(\vartheta(t), T) = \alpha_{1,2}^{(0)}(T) + \alpha_{1,2}^{(1)} \cos \vartheta(t) + \alpha_{1,2}^{(2)} \cos 2\vartheta(t) + \dots \quad (18)$$

where $\alpha_{1,2}^{(0)}(T)$ are the static average deviations from π of the retardation of the two wave plates, which in turn depends on temperature T , and $\alpha_{1,2}^{(1)}$ and $\alpha_{1,2}^{(2)}$ are the deviations from π of the retardation with, respectively, a one-revolution periodicity and a half-revolution periodicity. Contributions can be due to a wedge $\beta \lesssim 10^{-6}$ rad between the front and back surfaces of each wave plate coupled to a non-centered beam, a misalignment of the laser beam, the rotation axis and the normal to the wave plate surface and finally to a periodic de-centering of the wave plate during rotation. These effects are depicted in Figure 3. Each rotating wave plate must be aligned independently to minimise the above-mentioned spurious effects but this cannot be done at the nominal wavelength of the half-wave plates: a single rotating half-wave plate does not allow a measurement in extinction. The frequency doubled 532-nm beam is used for this reason. At 532 nm, 1064-nm half-wave plates behave as full-wave plates – with an extra contribution to $\alpha_{1,2}^{(0)}(T)$ due to dispersion; in this case, then, the presence of a single rotating 1064 nm half-wave plate leaves the polarisation direction fixed, allowing to work in extinction. The spurious effects in Figure 3, though, remain at 532 nm. Therefore, each rotating wave plate can be independently aligned with the 532-nm beam keeping the other

Figure 3: Different alignment issues which will generate spurious ellipticity harmonics of ν_w . In particular the left most and right most effects will generate a 4-th harmonic in $\psi(t)$

still. For alignment, the rotating wave plates are mounted on a 4-degree optical mount. A typical acceptable value for the spurious 4-th harmonic ellipticity induced by the rotating half-wave plates is $|\psi_{\text{spurious}}^{(4\text{-th})}(t)| \lesssim 10^{-5}$. This spurious ellipticity (amplitude and phase) can be determined by removing the substrate sample from the optical path; its value is to be vector-subtracted from the measurement with the sample. This subtraction determines the ultimate sensitivity of the polarimeter which is estimated to be about $|\psi_{\text{spurious}}^{(4\text{-th})}(t)|/5 \approx 2 \times 10^{-6}$ corresponding to an optical path difference sensitivity $S_{\Delta\mathcal{D}} = \int_{\text{sample}} \Delta n dz \lesssim 10^{-12}$ m.

However, as will be shown in the section Results, the sample contribution $\psi(t)$ is typically much larger than $\psi_{\text{spurious}}^{(4\text{-th})}(t)$.

Calibration

The rotating magnetic field is used to calibrate the polarimeter taking advantage of the Cotton-Mouton effect in air. Gases exhibit magnetic birefringence Δn_{CM} which is parametrised as

$$\Delta n_{\text{CM}} = \Delta n_u P B^2 \quad (19)$$

where P is the gas pressure (in atmospheres), B^2 is the square of the external dipolar magnetic field (in tesla) and Δn_u is the Cotton-Mouton specific for each gas. Assuming that air is mainly composed of 20% oxygen and 80% nitrogen one finds [4]

$$\Delta n_u^{(\text{air})} = 6.4 \times 10^{-13} \text{ T}^{-2} \text{ atm}^{-1}. \quad (20)$$

With the magnetic field installed on the setup parameterised by $\int_{\text{magnet}} B^2 dL = 5.13 \text{ T}^2\text{m}$ the induced ellipticity at 1064 nm is $|\psi_{\text{CM}}^{(\text{air})}| = 1.0 \times 10^{-5}$. The magnetic field is typically rotated at $\nu_B = 0.5$ Hz so that the frequency at which the ellipticity $\psi_{\text{CM}}^{(\text{air})}$ appears is $4\nu_w \pm 2\nu_B = 7$ Hz or 9 Hz depending on its relative rotation direction with respect to the half-wave plates.

2D mapping

For mapping the optical path difference induced by the birefringence of a sample, the sample is mounted on a horizontal-vertical mount with micrometer screws with a 2.5 cm range. 2-D maps with a typical step size of 2 mm of the induced ellipticity can therefore be taken. The spatial resolution is

limited by the beam spot size of about 0.5 mm diameter. For each sample, one can extract both the amplitude of the average birefringence along the sample thickness and its direction.

It must be noted that given the high refractive index of silicon of $n_{Si} = 3.55$ at 1064 nm there is a significant etalon effect (no anti-reflection coatings must be used). This effect multiplies the induced ellipticity by a factor in the range $0.8 \div 1.2$ but will not be considered in this paper.

Reflection measurements

Figure 4 shows a simplified scheme for reflection measurements. The principle is very similar to the transmission scheme.

Figure 4: Simplified scheme for reflection measurements. The beam enters the polarimeter through the output port of the polariser and is linearly polarised. The beam then passes through the ellipticity modulator and rotating half-wave plate reaching the mirror under investigation. After reflection the polarisation rotation is stopped by a second passage through the half-wave plate. The beam then passes a second time through the modulator and is then analysed by the polariser. The rejected beam is collected on a position sensitive photodiode to ensure that the reflected beam passes through the half-wave plate always in the same position.

The laser beam enters the polarimeter through the output polariser (analyser) shown in Figure 2 and is therefore linearly polarised. The beam then passes through the ellipticity modulator and the rotating half-wave plate HWP thereby reaching the sample to be measured in reflection. After reflection the beam returns through the half-wave plate and the polarisation stops rotating. A second pass through the ellipticity modulator doubles the effective modulation to $2\eta(t)$. Finally, the beam is analysed in extinction. In this scheme the output power is

$$P_{out}^{(refl.)}(t) = P_0 \left\{ \sigma^2 + |\psi(t) + 2\eta(t)|^2 \right\} = P_0 \left\{ \sigma^2 + 4|\eta(t)|^2 + \mathcal{R}e[4\eta(t)\psi^*(t)] + |\psi(t)|^2 \right\} \quad (21)$$

Here too the rotating half-wave plate will introduce harmonics in the total ellipticity $\psi_{tot}(t)$ just as in the transmission case. In this case, the contribution of $\psi_{spurious}^{(4-th)}$ to the 4-th harmonic of the total ellipticity $\psi_{tot}(t)$ cannot be determined by removing the sample. Therefore for each position of the beam on the sample two measurements are taken: one with the sample at $\vartheta_0 = 0^\circ$ and the second at $\vartheta_0 = 90^\circ$. For the two measurements the total ellipticities after the demodulation at ν_m will be

$$\psi_{total}^{(0^\circ)}(t) = \psi(t) + \psi_{spurious}(t) = i\psi_0 \sin 4\vartheta(t) + i\alpha(t) \sin [2\vartheta(t) + 2\vartheta_2] \quad (22)$$

$$\psi_{total}^{(90^\circ)}(t) = -\psi(t) + \psi_{spurious}(t) = -i\psi_0 \sin 4\vartheta(t) + i\alpha(t) \sin [2\vartheta(t) + 2\vartheta_2] \quad (23)$$

where the sample ellipticity changes sign between the two sample orientations.

By further demodulating $\psi_{\text{total}}(t)$ at $4\omega_w$, the semi-sum and semi-difference of the *in-phase* and *quadrature* components are taken thereby extracting separately $\psi_0^{(4\text{-th})}$ with its phase and $\psi_{0,\text{spurious}}^{(4\text{-th})}$ with its phase too.

During reflection measurements, attention must be taken to ensure that the reflected beam always passes through the same position on HWP otherwise $\psi_{\text{spurious}}(t)$ will change when changing the position of the sample or its azimuthal angle. For this reason a position-sensitive photo-diode (PSD) is mounted on the non-extinguished beam as can be seen in Figure 4.

Results

Fourier spectrum

Figure 5 shows a typical Fourier amplitude spectrum of the demodulated signal at ν_m . This particular spectrum refers to a transmission measurement but is very similar for reflection measurements. The amplitude is reported in optical path difference $\Delta\mathcal{D} = \int \Delta n dz$. In red is a spectrum without a sample and in blue is the same spectrum with a 1 mm thick silicon sample. The half-wave plates were rotating at $\nu_w = 2$ Hz and the magnetic field was rotating at $\nu_B = 0.5$ Hz in the same direction as the half-wave plates, resulting in a Cotton-Mouton peak of air at $\nu_{\text{CM}}^{(\text{air})} = 7$ Hz.

Figure 5: Typical demodulated optical path difference spectra, with the wave plates rotating at $\nu_w = 2$ Hz. Blue spectrum: 1-mm thick Si(100) sample; red spectrum: no sample.

As can be seen the first three harmonics of ν_w are completely superimposed in the red and the blue spectra, and do not depend on the presence of the silicon sample and nor does the Cotton-Mouton signal peak. The Cotton-Mouton peak indicates an optical path difference $\Delta\mathcal{D}_{\text{CM}} = 3.2 \times 10^{-12}$ m resulting in a measured $\Delta n_u^{(\text{air})} = \Delta\mathcal{D}_{\text{CM}} / \int_{\text{magnet}} B^2 dL = (6.3 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-13} \text{ T}^{-2}\text{m}^{-1}$ compatible with the value in (20). The fourth harmonic of ν_w is where the silicon sample generates an ellipticity signal. As can be seen, without the sample, the spurious peak corresponds to an optical path difference $\Delta\mathcal{D}_{\text{spurious}} = 3.2 \times 10^{-12}$ m whereas with the sample the optical path difference $\Delta\mathcal{D}_{\text{sample}} = 1.1 \times 10^{-10}$ m corresponds to an average birefringence over the thickness of $\Delta n = 1.1 \times 10^{-7}$.

In reflection measurements the ellipticity spectrum contains the same harmonics and is very similar except that a spectrum without the sample cannot be taken.

Figure 6: Birefringence maps of two 1-mm thick Si(100) crystalline samples. For all the points the same no-sample value has been vector subtracted.

2-D transmission maps

Figure 6, left and right, shows examples of birefringence maps integrated along the beam path of two Si(100) crystalline samples $2.5 \text{ cm} \times 2.5 \text{ cm}$, 1 mm thick. The samples were supported vertically without stress by a holder with a 1 mm groove. The birefringence maps were taken with a 2 mm step. The maps show a clear nonuniformity in birefringence both in value and in direction specific for each sample. All angles are covered, indicating that there is no connection to the crystalline planes. Note that here the birefringence axis directions for the two samples are at the moment undetermined to an additive angle.

Figure 7: Optical path difference maps for two reflecting samples. Left: a commercial silver mirror (protected); right: a dielectric mirror with 10^{-3} transmission. To get rid of spurious signal, each point is half the vector difference of two measurements taken with the sample oriented at 0° and 90° , respectively.

2-D reflection maps

With the attention reported in the section describing reflection measurements, two mirror samples are reported in Figure 7 as an example of the capability of the measuring system: a silver (protected) mirror and a dielectric mirror having transmission $T \approx 10^{-3}$. As the reflecting thickness is not known, here the optical path difference $\Delta\mathcal{D} = \int_{\text{reflector}} \Delta n dz$ is reported instead of the birefringence. Interestingly, the silver mirror has an optical path difference $\Delta\mathcal{D}$ of about a factor 50 smaller than the dielectric coating, indicating a significant stress. Furthermore, the percentage variation of the value of the optical path difference $\Delta\mathcal{D}$ over the surface of the mirror is much smaller than for the substrate measurements, as is also the direction of the birefringence. Again, the directions are all with an added arbitrary angle.

Comments and discussion

Substrate birefringence requirements

From KAGRA's experience a non uniform birefringence of the sapphire substrate in a plane perpendicular to the crystal's c -axis of about $\Delta n_{\text{KAGRA}} \approx 10^{-6}$ [5] over a round trip thickness $2d_{\text{KAGRA}} = 30$ cm was measured and caused serious problems in the sensitivity of the interferometer. The induced phase shift was of the order $\Delta\varphi_{\text{KAGRA}} \approx 1$ rad ($\lambda = 1064$ nm). Consider now the future Einstein Telescope detector: one of the substrate materials being considered for the low frequency cryogenic detector (ET-LF) is silicon, given its cubic crystalline structure with no birefringence axis. In literature point birefringences of $\Delta n_{\text{Si}} \approx 10^{-7}$ have been reported. Given the design thickness $d_{\text{ET-LF}} = 57$ cm, a phase shift of $\Delta\varphi_{\text{ET-LF}} \approx 0.5$ rad ($\lambda = 1550$ nm) will be induced, of the same order as for KAGRA. Considering, finally, that ET-LF is designed to be at least a factor 10 more sensitive than KAGRA, a birefringence of the ET-LF substrates of $\Delta n \approx 10^{-7}$ is clearly not small enough if this birefringence is non uniform: a value $\Delta n_{\text{Si}} < 10^{-8}$ will be necessary. In alternative, if a uniform substrate birefringence is present combined with the generally more uniform birefringence of the mirror coatings (see below), one can imagine aligning the global birefringence axis (global birefringence of substrate and mirror coatings combined assuming a stable finesse) with the polarisation of the beam, and a less stringent requirement can be accepted.

Coating birefringence

Mirror coatings are birefringent even at normal incidence. It is known that generally the higher the reflectivity of a coating, the lower the birefringence. In experiments using such mirrors [6, 7] the induced ellipticity per reflection is $\lesssim 10^{-6}$ whereas in lower-finesse mirrors [8] the induced ellipticity is higher. Another characteristic is that the coating birefringence has a rather uniform two dimensional map both in amplitude and direction. In a Fabry-Perot cavity the (uniform) birefringence of the two mirror coatings combine [9] thus acting as a single uniform birefringent medium whose axis can therefore be aligned with the polarisation of the incident light to minimize its effect. This characteristic allows aligning the polarisation with respect to birefringence of the cavity. In reference [8] the authors attribute this birefringence in mirror coatings to the layer closest to the substrate, suggesting that the cause is the stress between the first layer and the substrate.

Conclusions

In this paper we have presented a polarimeter for measuring two-dimensional birefringence maps of both substrate and reflective coatings.

Examples for crystalline silicon 1 mm thick showing a non uniform birefringence map distribution are reported. These samples were extracted from standard microelectronics wafers. The measured birefringence is of the order of $\Delta n_{\text{Si}} \approx 10^{-7}$. Studies are ongoing on how to grow better silicon mono crystals (private communication: <https://www.ikz-berlin.de>) to satisfy the goal birefringence of $\Delta n_{\text{Si}} < 10^{-8}$.

We have also presented optical path difference maps $\Delta\mathcal{D}$ for two types of mirrors: a silver (protected) mirror and a dielectric mirror with transmission $T \approx 10^{-3}$. The silver mirror shows a smaller optical path difference of about a factor 50 with respect to the dielectric sample.

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